

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE
THROUGH MASS MEDIA

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Abstract: The use of mass media in the field of foreign language teaching is not a new phenomenon. Nowadays using mass media in the process of self-education is spread widely and also it is an important tool used by foreign language teachers. Technological progress, the communication revolution, the spread of the Internet, and the development of new media and mobile technologies offer modern and more effective methods of language education. This article reviews the conditions relating to the relationship between mass. media and language learning.

Key words: Mass media foreign language teaching, media education.

Media today have an enormous impact. They have become so important that it is rarely that we can live without them. So everyday, everyone is affected by the Mass Media in some way or another, when you study a textbook for school, when you turn on the radio in your car, when you see a movie on TV, etc.

Despite the criticism of the mass media, most people agree that mass media do a superior job in reporting the news and informing the public. It's our task as teachers to help students and pupils understand this information, transmit it to the coming generations and try to use it for education purposes. So in the last few decades, the model of foreign language teaching has changed fundamentally. So present time role of teachers' also has changed. They must be fully aware that the application of modern technologies as didactic instruments does not bring the desired effects if it is not based on a well thought out methodical process. First and

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foremost it is necessary to make a change in all aspects of teaching, and therefore broadly understood educational philosophy, Foreign language teachers should create conditions that enable the mastery of new technology. If the person conducting the classes does not have adequate knowledge and practice, then he/she is more willing to return to traditional didactic forms. Currently, the teachers of foreign languages have OHP projectors, allowing multimedia presentations, CD and DVD players or interactive boards so at present, the Internet has become the dominant methodological tool used in foreign language teaching. And a statement that the Internet has contributed to the revolution of foreign language teaching can be truly posed. A computer with the Internet connection is becoming an effective instrument that allows real-time access to authentic materials that are created by all Internet users. Thus, it gives teachers the opportunity to use educational solutions in any didactic or cultural context, or finally in relation to the desired content. The dynamic progress of knowledge in the area of all scientific disciplines causes a fact that the knowledge acquired during studies "is getting older. This means that people must constantly update their knowledge to create a high degree of professionalism throughout their professional life. New technologies have been introduced into the catalog of methodological instruments of foreign language teaching relatively recently, but they have immediately contributed to the effectiveness of foreign language teaching process. It is not only an adaptation of the technological possibilities noticed for the discussed needs, but it is also an integral element of the civilization development. In addition, the use of multimedia and audiovisual instruments contributes not only to a significant improvement of foreign language teaching, but also to their greater attractiveness. In this way, the knowledge transferred and the competencies shaped are more willingly observed and comprehended by the students. The catalog of didactic instruments, which are based on modern technologies, gives the teacher the opportunity to choose the ones that are most effective in his/her opinion.

Using various kinds of Media in the classroom has always been a challenge, and how to bring these Media in the classroom is more than a challenge. Students and teachers should be able to use in their classrooms different media through different technologies. Media provide teachers and students with creative and practical ideas. They enable teachers to meet various needs and interests of their students and also it provides students with a lot of language practice through activities using newspapers, magazines, radio, TV, movies, books, Internet and tasks which develop reading, writing, speaking and listening skills. They entertain students and encourage reading English in general, both inside and outside the classroom, promoting extensive reading by giving the students the confidence, the motivation and the ability to continue their reading outside the classroom. The most commonly used media classification included in education is divided into:

- auditory media, which affect the recipient via the ear canal, which is used while listening to music, radio, mp3 files.
- visual media, which affect the viewer through the visual channel, due to the use of the image, and a moving image such as a movie,
- audiovisual media, which affect the recipients via their sensory channels.

The advantage and power of teaching methods using mass media and multimedia is manifested in the fact that they are associated more with entertainment than with an obligation or a chore. Thus, mass media based teaching is being widely promoted in educational institutions and other places where foreign languages are taught and where the computers, Internet networks, multimedia boards and other electronic information carriers are implemented and as common as traditional and new means of communication.

REFERENCES:

1. Beckert Christine (1992), Getting Started in Mass Media, National Textbook Company, Chicago, IL.
2. Biagi Shirley (1999), Media / Impact, Wadsworth New York.

3. Garrett (1991), Technology in the Service Language Learning, Modern Language Journal.
4. Merrill Paul (2002), Computers in Education, Allyn & Bacon, Boston, MA.
5. Morrison Gary, Lowther Deborah, DeMeulle Lisa (1999), Integrating Computer Technology into the Classroom, Prentice-Hall, Inc, New Jersey.
6. Willets (1998), Integrating Technology into the Foreign Language Curriculum. A teacher training manual, Washington, Center for Applied Linguistics.

